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Ethical Component of Library Competencies Design: Professional View

Objective. Substantiation of the ethical component place in the set of modern librarians' key competencies. **Methods.** Conclusions and results have been obtained due to use of dialectical, socio-communicative, analytical-review methods, methods of systematization, comparative analysis, bibliographic analysis, content analysis and document analysis. **Results.** The need to supplement the educational standards on the speciality 029 "Information, Library and Archival Affairs" bachelor's and master's levels with ethical component – the librarian's understanding of the principles and values of information and professional ethics, academic integrity and capacity to follow them was justified. **Conclusions.** Adherence to professional ethical norms and the spread of the academic integrity culture creates the conditions for the demand for other librarian's professional competencies because it provides the value of knowledge and personal theoretical and applied achievements. Given the urgent need to spread the culture of academic integrity in the scientific and educational environment and the lack of relevant educational goals in bachelor and master educational standards, Ukrainian Library Association offers the scientific and methodological basis for the formation of the academic integrity culture as an important competence of a modern librarian within the framework of implementation of the compensatory function.

Keywords: professional competencies; librarian; academic integrity; All-Ukrainian public organization "Ukrainian Library Association"

Introduction

The trend towards universalization of professional library education, caused by the rapid development of information technology, the crisis of the library profession and its transformation by strengthening the information and archival components, raises the issue of determining the competencies that potential employers expect future librarians to have, as certain competencies ultimately determine the library environment development (Panda & Panda, 2019, p. 365).

Core competencies relevant to the professional development goals and consistent with the library's mission and vision determine the guidelines of professional library education and act as a necessary condition, the basis for further updating of educational programs, curricula, and disciplines.

At the same time, changes in the social role of the librarian himself, who transforms from an information scientist to a knowledge "facilitator," and the constant improvement and modernization of professional activity technological principles lead to increased scientific attention not only and not so much to "hard skills" (work with information in various formats, use of a wide range of digital tools, resources and technologies, launching and managing electronic libraries, etc.) but to skills that qualify as "soft" as well: be able to work in a team and autonomously, think critically, generate new ideas, develop and implement projects, etc. (Hranchak, 2021, p. 13). A special role in the complex of soft skills is played by the ethical component, which is directly related to the social responsibility of the library profession. It is the adherence to ethical principles that determines the implementation of the whole set of other professional competencies for the benefit of society and the individual.

The aim of the article is to determine the place of the ethical component in the vision of key competencies of a modern librarian by the professional community.

Methods and Materials

The results of the study have been obtained due to use of dialectical and social communication methods, which allowed to consider professional library education in its development and relationship with the transformation of library practice, as well as from the standpoint of compliance with current needs of libraries and their clients; analytical review method useful to study the professional literature; methods of systematization and comparative analysis, which were necessary due to the need to compare different views on the training of librarians and identify common general trends; bibliographic analysis, the heuristic potential of which proved to be useful for outlining the theoretical basis of the study; methods of content analysis and document analysis when working with sources. The source base of the study consisted of current professional publications on selected issues, legal documents, specialized Internet resources.

Results and Discussion

Given the transformation of the profession, caused by the widespread introduction of modern Internet technologies and online service in library practice, supplementing library specialities with archival and documentary components, diversification of forms and methods of library work due to intensifying of libraries' project activities, issues of content training of librarians are in the focus of scientific attention of many domestic and foreign scholars and library practitioners, are discussed on the pages of professional scientific publications and at the level of relevant library organizations.

The predominant attention of foreign researchers (Atanda et al., 2021; Panda & Panda, 2019; Kaur & Sharma, 2018; Santos, 2018; Swapna & Biradar, 2016; Bin Hashim & Mokhtar, 2012; Nonthacumjane, 2011) is paid to computer, media, information, and communication competencies of librarians, their ability to self-development and solving problems of management and organization of production processes.

The ethical component among the list of competencies required for a librarian is insufficiently represented in the professional scientific publications, although it is mentioned by some researchers (Manu et al., 2018; Nonthacumjane, 2011; Tanloet & Tuamsuk, 2011).

In particular, the researchers (Manu et al., 2018) provide an overview of core competencies for library and information science professionals developed by various national and international library professional associations and networks, emphasizing the need for future librarians to develop knowledge and principles of information ethics along with competencies such as knowledge of information systems and technologies, information literacy, ability to provide information services, information retrieval and data analysis, understanding of information architecture, approaches to data organization, information and knowledge and providing access to them, information and knowledge management, etc. In general, these skills can be organized in five groups of competencies: IT competencies, organization and management of library collections, organization and implementation of library and information services, management and leadership, ethics and further training.

Issues of ethics and social responsibility are considered by scholars in the context of the general skills of the librarians (Nonthacumjane, 2011) and their personal qualities (Tanloet & Tuamsuk, 2011).

As for the scientific achievements of domestic scientists, their conclusions with some clarifications are mostly correlated with the results obtained by colleagues abroad.

First of all, in this context it is worth mentioning a number of domestic scientific papers on the analysis of higher education standards in the speciality 029 "Information, Library and Archival

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Affairs,” development of relevant educational programs in higher education institutions, substantiation of relevant components (Hranchak, 2021, 2017; Makeeva, 2021, Matviienko, Tsyvin, & Humenchuk, 2021; Novalska & Kasian, 2021; Davydova & Marina, 2020; Kukhtiak, 2019; Solyanik, 2018, 2016).

The vision of leading domestic scholars and practitioners of the set of the most important competencies that a librarian should possess is reflected in the approved standards of higher education on the speciality 029 “Information, Library and Archival Affairs.” The documents define the general and professional competencies of the future librarian, as well as learning outcomes, which can be systematized into groups of personal, managerial, communicative, information technology competencies and supplemented by a group of research competencies at the level of Doctor of Philosophy.

Despite the active scientific development of issues related to the profile of the modern librarian and the reform of library and information education, scientists still note the “contradictions between: modern labour market requirements for training of information, library and archival professionals and the actual level of their training; educational goals outlined in normative and program documents, and functional possibilities of the existing educational and methodical maintenance for their realization; necessity of formation of readiness for professional activity of bachelors of information, library and archival business in higher education institutions and need of updating the educational and methodological support for their training” (Kukhtiak, 2019, p. 4).

The contradiction between the needs of the labour market and the existing educational goals outlined in the regulations and policy documents should be added to the above. In particular, this applies to the “lost” in educational standards on the speciality 029 “Information, Library and Archives” bachelor’s and master’s degree, but a key for the librarian an ethical component, his understanding of values and adherence to the principles of academic integrity, following the principles of information ethics.

Mention of ethical principles of library and information activities can be found only in the general competencies of the professional educational standard at the level of Doctor of Philosophy: “an ability to solve complex problems in information, library and archival affairs on the basis of a systematic scientific worldview and general cultural outlook in compliance with the principles of professional ethics and academic integrity” (*Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, 2021*). However, such wording somehow narrows the scope of the principles of professional ethics and academic integrity, limiting it to situations of complex problems, while, ideally, these principles should be at the heart of all library and information activities and professional responsibilities.

In the professional library environment (Makeeva, 2021; Horoshok & Zhovtko, 2020; Karpenko, 2016) mastery of the code of ethics and conduct, understanding of ethics and values of the library profession are determined as competencies, necessary for a librarian along with the ability to analyse, evaluate, compare, structure information, use modern information and communication technologies, manage information resources, complete the fund with traditional and electronic media in accordance with the standards of librarianship in Ukraine, think logically and critically, ability to work in a team, solve problems of varying complexity, take initiative, constantly improve their educational level, etc.

Adherence to professional ethical norms and the spread of a culture of academic integrity creates the conditions for the demand for all further professional competencies of a librarian because it provides the value of knowledge and personal theoretical and applied achievements. According to Makeeva (2021), “ethical competence represents and regulates the main actions that are consolidated in the skills, traditions, principles of life and professional activity, mental states, actions, deeds, and qualities of a university librarian” (p. 44). The need to find information and

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access knowledge loses its relevance if the key to success is not professional knowledge and skills, but the ability to adapt, personal loyalty and devotion, the ability to build a network of useful connections and so on. Corrupt traditions devalue professional knowledge, which leads to the spread of imitation practices during training. Under such conditions, students no longer try to find the necessary information (lose of relevance of information retrieval activities, information evaluation), create a secondary original information product based on it (creativity, research skills, ability to analyse, synthesize information, use methodological tools) and etc. Their main purpose is to simulate the creation of the required product, which ultimately causes reputational damage to science and leads to an overall decrease in the level of professional competence of graduates. Libraries can play a key role in spreading the culture of academic integrity, so the formation of understanding of its principles and adherence to values is one of the basic competencies for future librarians, the formation of which should permeate his training at all levels of higher education.

In this context, the in-service training programs for librarians (Bruï, Kulyk, Nazarovets, & Soshynska, 2020; Voskoboinikova-Huzieva et al., 2018), methodological advice (Savenkova & Chukanova, 2016) and the librarians competence profile on academic integrity (Bruï, Savenkova, & Chukanova, 2019), developed by experts of the Ukrainian Library Association (hereinafter – ULA), deserve attention because their content allows us to draw conclusions about the required for library practitioners competencies, the lack of which is observed in the professional environment.

The approved profile of librarians' competencies in academic integrity reveals their content, that consists of:

- *understanding* the basics and principles of scientific communication; principles, methods and means of organizing the educational and scientific processes of the university; interaction of participants of educational and scientific processes of the university; current trends in the development of the academic integrity movement in Ukraine and the world; interaction and mutual influence of all components and participants of scientific and educational communication in the process of formation and development of a virtuous academic environment; features of the process of academic publication; principles of formation and operation of scientometric indicators and tools; interaction and mutual influence of participants of the process of scientific communication on observance/violation of the principles of academic integrity in scientometric indicators; the impact of open access on the formation and dissemination of a culture of academic integrity;

- *knowledge* of general principles and foundations of academic integrity; authoritative domestic and international informational scientific and educational sources; general methods and means of information retrieval; features of search in library catalogues; features of search in specific domestic and international databases of authoritative informational scientific and educational sources; basics of intellectual property, including copyright; features of intellectual property, in particular copyright, in research (Ukrainian and international context); principles, rules and features of open access; requirements and rules for registration of scientific and educational works (Ukrainian and international context); standards and rules of references and citations in scientific and educational works (Ukrainian and international context); standards and rules of bibliographic description (Ukrainian and international context); basics of scientometrics and bibliometrics; methods of teaching educational material for certain categories of students;

- *ability* to teach tutoring material; organize practical classes; control the level of knowledge and skills of certain categories of students (Bruï, Savenkova, & Chukanova, 2019, p. 7-8).

The relevance of the formation of the competence of the librarian in academic integrity is also confirmed by the ULA's participation in the Academic Integrity Project in Ukraine (SAIUP) and the Academic Integrity in School Project (SAISS) from the American Councils for

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International Education in cooperation with the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine and the USA Embassy in Ukraine (Hranchak & Soshynska, 2019, p. 119).

Thus, in conditions of urgent need to spread the culture of academic integrity in the scientific and educational environment and the lack of defined relevant educational goals in professional educational standards specialties, ULA in frames of implementation of the compensatory function fills the gap and offers scientific and methodological tools for forming an academic integrity culture of library and information staff.

Conclusions

The issues of designing a profile of a librarian who would meet the needs of library practice are in the focus of attention of many domestic and foreign theorists and practitioners of library affairs. At the same time, only some scholars emphasize the need to form a set of competencies in information ethics and academic integrity in a modern librarian. There is no ethical component in the national educational standards in the speciality 029 “Information, Library and Archival Affairs” of master’s and bachelor’s levels, which complicates the formalization of relevant educational goals in educational programs for bachelors and masters of information, library and archival affairs. Given the existing gap and taking into account the needs of practical library activities, Ukrainian Library Association provides a scientific and methodological basis and systematically implements measures to form a culture of academic integrity in scientific, educational and professional environments. Theoretical conclusions in the field of library science and the ULA experience confirm the importance of supplementing bachelor’s and master’s level educational standards on the speciality 029 “Information, Library and Archival Affairs” with ethical components – the librarian’s understanding of principles and values of information and professional ethics, academic integrity and ability to follow them.

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Етичний компонент дизайну компетентностей бібліотечного фаху: професійний погляд

Мета. Обґрунтування місця етичного компоненту в наборі ключових компетентностей сучасного бібліотекаря. **Методика.** Висновки і результати отримані шляхом використання діалектичного, соціальнокомунікаційного аналітико-оглядового методів, методів систематизації, компаративного аналізу, бібліографічного аналізу, аналізу контенту та аналізу документів. **Результати.** Обґрунтовано потребу доповнення освітніх стандартів за спеціальністю 029 "Інформаційна, бібліотечна та архівна справа" освітніх рівнів бакалавра і магістра етичним компонентом – розумінням бібліотекарем принципів і цінностей інформаційної і професійної етики, академічної доброчесності та слідування їм. **Висновки.** Дотримання професійних етичних норм і поширення культури академічної доброчесності формує умови для затребуваності інших професійних компетентностей бібліотечного працівника, адже передбачає цінність знань і особистих теоретичних і прикладних досягнень. За гострої потреби поширення в науково-освітньому середовищі культури академічної доброчесності й відсутності визначених у фахових освітніх стандартах бакалавра і магістра відповідних освітніх цілей науково-методичне підґрунтя для формування культури академічної доброчесності як важливої компетентності бібліотечно-інформаційних працівників пропонує ВГО "Українська бібліотечна асоціація" в рамках реалізації компенсаторної функції.

Ключові слова: професійні компетентності; бібліотекар; академічна доброчесність; ВГО "Українська бібліотечна асоціація"

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